

Ehrenfest Paradox and the meaning of its non-resolution

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Abstract: In the special theory of relativity proper lengths of rods and rulers remain unaltered. However, non co-moving rods and rulers (appear to) contract along the line of movement. This contraction is asserted to be as real as any conceivable physical measurement that is made by the reference frame with respect to which the rods and rulers are moving. It is well recognised that the contraction is a result of mismatch in synchronization of spatially separated clocks. The Ehrenfest paradox highlights the anomalies created by (apparent) length contraction that is real for the non-comoving frame yet non-existent for the comoving frame. Ehrenfest, a reputed theoretical physicist of his times, himself did not offer a solution to the paradox, indicating that the paradox is a critique of the special relativity theory. There is no consensus on the resolution of the paradox except evasive ones such as the clocks on the circumference cannot be synchronised by any acceptable procedure or the impossibility of maintaining rigidity during the transition. The original paradox proposed by Ehrenfest, envisaged contraction of the circumference. The counterview proposed by Einstein that the rulers on the circumference contracted, leading to a measurement of a larger circumference, only exasperates the paradox. Thus the paradox remains unresolved causing doubts on the maintainability of the theory of special relativity. The difficulties that preclude the possibility of an acceptable synchronisation in the rotating frame lead to an impossibility of observing any reality, absolute or otherwise. This is because without synchronisation of spatially separated clocks, it is not possible to measure the length of a moving rod. Since there must be a reality, absolute or otherwise, we suggest that there must be a synchronisation that corresponds to reality.

1. Introduction:

Within the formulation of the theory of Special Relativity, the apparent length contraction of non-comoving objects, with no contraction in their comoving (proper) reference frames, has been a matter of intrigue [1]. The mathematical formulations maintain a certain consistency, in that the events of interaction between objects (like collision or passing of the rod through the slot), have only changes in coordinates. The integrity (physical nature) of the events itself is unaffected. This is explained in the resolution of the rod-slot paradox. The determination whether the rod will pass through the slot or not, using classical physics and proper lengths (without any contraction) and the determination by relativistic physics, using the LT and length contraction formulations, yield the same result [2]. Only the angle between the length of the rod and the length of the slot is altered by the relativistic kinematics. This alteration is closely associated with the relativity of simultaneity envisaged by the theory of relativity. In essence, an event that occurred at (x,t) in the comoving frame will be observed by the other reference frame to occur at $((x-vt),t)$ by classical considerations and $((x-vt)\gamma, (t- vx/c^2)\gamma)$ by relativistic considerations. This change of observed coordinates doesn't alter the event itself

that is the passing of the leading edge of the rod through the slot's forward edge. In classical Physics the trailing edge of the rod will pass through the rear edge of the slot at the same instant in both the reference frames (as the leading edge of the rod passing through the forward edge of the slot). In relativistic Physics the instant is altered by the Lorentz Transformation and due to this the angle between the lengths of the rod and slot is observed to be different [2]. However, these changes in coordinates and angles do not alter the events, thus if it is determined that the rod will pass through the slot by classical calculations, the same holds good for relativistic Physics also [2]. This is similar to Ehrenfest Theorem [3], on the validity of classical mechanics within quantum mechanics in the context of *expected values*.

Ehrenfest [4] considered a rotating circular object. A reference frame K with respect to which the circular object is rotating will observe a contraction of the circumference and no change in the radial dimensions. If we consider a circular slot (of same proper radius), in the reference frame K, the same will be observed by the rotating object, K', to have a shorter circumference. Thus when the rotating object tries to pass through the slot, there will be clear passage according to K, and there will be collision according to K'.

Ehrenfest, a reputed mathematician of his times, did not offer any solution to the paradox, thereby leaving it as a possible critique of the special theory of relativity. To a large extent, this paradox remains unresolved.

2. Reciprocal Length Contraction:

Consider two long rods (rulers) in uniform relative motion along their length. They constitute two inertial reference frames (K and K') that are in uniform relative motion with a speed v . They set up their origins at points that coincide at an instance. The clocks at $x = 0$ and $x' = 0$ are set to $t = 0$ and $t' = 0$ when the points $x = 0$ and $x' = 0$ coincide. This is the usual notation in the exposition of the special relativity theory.

The geometry of the situation demands that at any given time t in K, the origin of K' is located at $x = vt$ (as observed by K). If any event happens at (x,t) in K, the same event's spatial coordinate x' will be measured by $x-vt$ save any calibration issues between the frames regarding length measurements. In other words $(x-vt)$ will be a measure of x' . That means $x' = (x-vt)*a$ where a is the proportionality constant that is a reflection of the misalignment in the calibration of the rulers of K and K'.

In classical Physics $a = 1$ and $x' = (x-vt)$. In relativistic physics

$$x' = (x-vt)*\gamma \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$\text{where } \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-(v^2/c^2)}$$

By symmetry of the Lorentz transformation and in accordance with the special theory of relativity, the corresponding equation between x on the lhs becomes

$$x = (x'+vt')*\gamma \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Combining equations (1) and (2) we get

$$x = \{ (x-vt)*\gamma + vt' \}*\gamma \text{ ----- (3)}$$

By substituting for t' from the Lorentz Transformation , that is $t' = \{t-(vx/c^2)\}*\gamma$ into (3), the correctness of equation (3) is easily verified by grouping x and t terms. (noting that $\gamma^2 = 1/\{1-(v^2/c^2)\}$)

$$\begin{aligned} x &= [(x-vt)*\gamma + v\{t-(vx/c^2)\}*\gamma]*\gamma \\ &= \gamma^2 [x(1-v^2/c^2) - vt + vt] = x \gamma^2 (1-v^2/c^2) = x \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting equation (3) as

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x-vt})*\gamma^2 + \mathbf{vt}'\gamma \text{ ----- (4)}$$

In classical physics $t = t'$ and $\gamma = 1$

A close inspection of equation (4), reveals that the length $(x-vt)$ is corrected twice (i.e. γ^2) by the calibration factor γ because of the theory that rulers of K' are contracted by the factor γ as observed by K (first correction) and the rulers of K are contracted by the factor γ as observed by K'(second correction). Final observation of x on the lhs of equation (4) is by irf K, and the x appearing in the rhs of equation (4) is also by IRF K.

Thus correcting x twice by the factor γ , yields mathematically the 'correct' result. The same doesn't make meaningful sense from a physical point of view.

3. Integrity of event characteristics under different transformations.

A wave front propagating along x axis has the intensity given by the below equation

$$I = I_0 \sin 2\pi [(x-ct)/\lambda] \text{ ----- (5)}$$

where c is the propagation speed of light and λ is the wave length.

When transformed by Galilean transformation $x' = (x-vt)$, $t' = t$, $c^* = (c-v)$ and $\lambda^* = \lambda$

the above equation becomes $I = I_0 \sin 2\pi [(x' - c^*t')/\lambda^*]$, substituting for x', t' and c*, we get

$$I = I_0 \sin 2\pi [(x-ct)/\lambda] \text{ ----- (6)}$$

The intensity I at the space time point remains unaltered

When transformed by Lorentz Transformation, with $x^L = (x-vt)\gamma$, $t^L = (t-(vx/c^2))\gamma$, $c^L = c$ and $\lambda^L = \lambda ((c+v)/(c-v))^{(1/2)}$, we get

$I = I_0 \sin 2\pi [(x^L - c^L t^L)/\lambda^L]$, substituting for x^L , t^L and λ^L from the transformation equations, we get

$$I = I_0 \sin 2\pi [(x-ct)/\lambda] \text{ ----- (7)}$$

Thus we find that coordinate transformations do not alter the events at all, in this case the magnitude of the intensity at a given space-time point. This is explained in more detail in [5]

4. Speed of Light with respect to source and receptor.

Special relativity theory assumes that the speed of light with respect to source and receptor are same through out the propagation from source to receptor at every segment of the propagation. It has been shown [6] that the results obtained by the theory of special relativity are just a mean or average of the two results, viz when the speed of light is c with respect to the source and the speed of light is c with respect to the receptor. Thus it is possible that when the speed of light is c with respect to the source, in the vicinity of the source and the speed of light is c with respect to the receptor, in the vicinity of the receptor, the results obtained will be same as that obtained by the special theory of relativity [6].

5. Ehrenfest Paradox

The Ehrenfest Paradox [4], requires that the circumference of the rotating disk is less than $2\pi r$ as observed from a reference frame outside of the rotating frame. When we consider a ring with a circular hollow space and a corresponding solid circular disk, both with the same proper radius, when the solid circular disk is rotating and trying to pass through the hollow ring, the situation is akin to the rod slot paradox [2].

However, a resolution of the rod slot paradox was obtained in [2] with the relativity of simultaneity (ros) and a change in angle of the rod as it approaches the slot, a similar or any other solution is not conceivable in the case of the rotating disk passing through the hollow circular ring.

The rotating solid disk will expect that it will be unable to pass through the hollow disk and the hollow disk will expect that the rotating disk will pass through.

This is because, once a contraction of moving rods is proposed as a measurable reality from the non co-moving frame [1], it has to be so in every such situation for physical laws to be applicable universally.

But since there can be only one reality, viz the passing of the disk through the hollow disk, or the collision when it attempted to pass, the contraction is precluded. Therefore, apparent length contraction is logically incorrect.

A correct determination whether the disk will pass or collide is possible only with an absolute synchronisation scheme that is universal and absolute.

6. Conclusion

With the above discussion in section 5, the only possible solution is that suggested in section 4, viz the speed of light is c with respect to the source, in the vicinity of the source and the speed of light is c with respect to the receptor, in the vicinity of the receptor. Such a view will maintain a universal synchronisation scheme as also detailed in [7].

References

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